

Application of INPRO Methodology to Assess Economic Feasibility of Proposed Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant

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Abstract—International Project on Innovative Nuclear Reactors and Fuel Cycles (INPRO) ensures that nuclear energy is available to meet the energy needs of the 21st century in a sustainable manner. It takes a holistic approach to assess innovative nuclear systems in seven areas of which economics is the primary concern. In order to contribute to sustainable development, energy and related products and services from any system must be affordable and available. The cost to the consumer must be competitive with that of low cost alternatives. Bangladesh being one of the energy deprived but economically uprising countries of the sub-continent plans to produce sufficient electricity to meet its internal demand with appropriate growth by 2030. The Power System Master Plan 2010 aims to meet more than half of the primary energy demand using indigenous resources. The other half is to be managed by imported coal, liquefied natural gas and fissile materials. In this study, the INPRO methodology has been applied to assess the economic feasibility of Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant from a newcomer country perspective considering other available options. Several dimensions of economic feasibility have been studied and some suggestions have been made for sustainable growth in the power sector of Bangladesh.

Index Terms—INPRO Methodology; Nuclear Power; Nuclear Newcomer; Rooppur Nuclear Power Plan; Economic Feasibility; Levelized Unit Electricity Cost; Internal Rate of Return; Return of Investment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea of nuclear power program for Bangladesh (then East Pakistan) was first conceived in 1961 and Rooppur site, 200 km north-west of Dhaka in Pabna district was selected in 1963 out of twelve possible sites. There were two independent electric power grids in the two different east and west zones of the province without any interconnection between them. So the Rooppur site, downstream of the Hardinge Bridge over the Ganges (Padma), was thus a natural choice for a nuclear power plant (NPP). Initial negotiations started in the early 60's with US and Soviet suppliers which could not be materialized due to political unrest in the region. After getting independence in 1971, the concept of first nuclear power plant remained a dream until 2010, when implementation of NPP project was reflected in the electoral manifestos of all major political

parties in 2008 [1]. The decision of the government to revive the Rooppur Nuclear Power Project (RNPP) was justified in view of the serious energy and power crises faced during that time. Since then several pre-project survey activities have been carried out and now we are in a stage where the NPP project is not only a dream, but a reality to be implemented in near future. Before jumping into such a large project with huge investment requirements, proper techno-economic justification needs to be made. The broad aims of this study are to assess and justify the economic feasibility of nuclear power from a developing country perspective and apply internationally approved financial models and simulation mechanism to help decision making process.

II. BANGLADESH POWER SECTOR

Bangladesh's energy infrastructure is quite small, insufficient and poorly managed. The per capita energy consumption in Bangladesh is one of the lowest (321 kWh) [2] in the world. Noncommercial energy sources, such as wood fuel, animal waste, and crop residues, are estimated to account for over half of the country's energy consumption. Bangladesh has small reserves of oil and coal, but very large natural gas resources. Commercial energy consumption is mostly natural gas (around 66%), followed by oil, hydropower and coal [3].

Fig. 1. Bangladesh installed generation capacity by fuel type (Aug. 2014) [4]

Electricity is the major source of power for most of the country's economic activities. Bangladesh's installed electric generation capacity was 10,618 MW in August, 2014; only three-fourth of which is considered to be 'available' and almost half of the generation facilities belong to the private sector mainly established for meeting peak hour demands for a limited time period. Only 62% of the population has access to electricity. Problems in the Bangladesh's electric power sector include corruption in administration, high system losses and delays in completion of new plants, low plant efficiencies, erratic power supply, electricity theft, blackouts, and shortages of funds for power plant maintenance. Overall, the country's generation plants have been unable to meet system demand over the past decade. Government has taken short, medium and long term plan. Under the short term plan, rental power plants will be installed using liquid fuels/gas and capable to produce electricity within 12-24 months. Total 1,653 MW generation capacities have been installed by this time from rental power plants.

Fig. 2. Bangladesh Projected Generation Mix in 2030 as of PSMP 2010

In order to develop the Bangladesh power sector, a Power Sector Master Plan (PSMP) was put in place in 2010. It reveals that in order to attain 8% GDP, the electricity demand would be 34,000 MW by the year 2030. The PSMP 2010 includes an optimum power development plan and identification of the potential power plant sites based on the fuel diversification study as shown in Fig. 2. The aggregated investments for the development of the generation, transmission and related facilities are found to be at Taka 4.8 trillion (US\$ 69.5 billion). The annual average of the investment amounts to Tk 241 billion (US\$ 3.5 billion).

INPRO METHODOLOGY

International Project on Innovative Nuclear Reactors and Fuel Cycles (INPRO) was established in the year 2000 to bring together technology holders and users so that they can jointly consider the international and national actions required for ensuring sustainability of nuclear energy through innovations in technology and/or institutional arrangements. This methodology identifies a set of basic principles, user requirements and criteria in a hierarchical manner as the basis for the assessment of an innovative nuclear system. INPRO takes a holistic approach to assess innovative nuclear systems in seven areas which are economics, infrastructure, waste

management, proliferation resistance, physical protection, environment and safety. In order to apply INPRO Economic Assessment in an energy system the planning study or energy scenario, which sets out the anticipated growth of energy demand as a function of time and which identifies the available energy supply options and the role of a nuclear energy system (NES) in meeting the energy demand projection, is required. INPRO basic principle in the area of economics is that energy and related products and services from nuclear energy systems shall be affordable and available. The cost of energy supplied by nuclear energy systems, taking all relevant costs and credits into account, C_N , must be competitive with that of alternative energy sources, C_A , that are available for a given application in the same time frame and geographical region or jurisdiction [5]. The total investment required to design, construct and commission nuclear energy systems, including interest during construction, should be such that the necessary investment funds can be raised. The risk of investment in nuclear energy systems should be acceptable to investors. As for any large scale project, there are many risks that can impinge on an NPP project. Innovative nuclear energy systems should also be compatible with meeting the requirements of different markets.

ECONOMICS OF NUCLEAR POWER GENERATION

The economics of new nuclear power plants is a controversial subject, since there are diverging views on this topic, and multi-billion dollar investments ride on the choice of an energy source. Nuclear power plants typically have high capital costs for building the plant, but low fuel costs and low external costs, namely carbon tax [6].

Assessing the relative costs of new generating plants utilizing different technologies is a complex matter and the results depend crucially on location. Coal is, and will probably remain, economically attractive in countries such as China, the USA and Australia with abundant and accessible domestic coal resources as long as carbon emissions are cost-free. Gas is also competitive for base-load power in many places, particularly using combined-cycle plants, though rising gas prices have removed much of the advantage. Nuclear power plants are expensive to build but relatively cheap to run. In many places, nuclear energy is competitive with fossil fuels as a means of electricity generation. Waste disposal and decommissioning costs are included in the operating costs. If the social, health and environmental costs of fossil fuels are also taken into account, the economics of nuclear power are outstanding.

TABLE I. COMPARISON AMONG DIFFERENT ENERGY GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES

Technology	Unit Size	Lead Time	Capital Cost	Operating Cost	Fuel
CCGT	Medium	Short	Low	Low	High
Coal	Large	Long	High	Low	Medium
Nuclear	Huge	Long	High	Low	Low
Hydro	Huge	Long	Very High	Very Low	Nil
Wind	Small	Short	High	Medium	Nil

Nuclear power and gas are currently the two most competitive electricity generation options upon the introduction of carbon pricing in liberalized electricity markets. However, nuclear power does not necessarily become the most profitable as carbon prices rise. The competitiveness of nuclear energy depends on significant but not overly high carbon prices. Even though the profitability of nuclear power increases in this scenario, its competitiveness against gas decreases. This is because the profitability of gas actually improves disproportionately with high and very high carbon prices (assuming that no carbon capture and storage is introduced). The competitiveness of nuclear energy against gas also declines rapidly with falling gas prices, which almost unilaterally determine the profitability of gas. A qualitative comparison among different generation technologies has been made in Table I.

RESULTS

In this section, several important economic parameters are calculated and these parameters are then used as input for an assessment of the economics of RNPP according to the INPRO methodology in the context of planned NES in Bangladesh. Input data for a calculation of the main economic parameters are shown in Table 2 for three selected types of power plants that are available in Bangladesh as future energy sources: two reactors of the type AES-2006 (VVER-1200) and, as alternative energy sources, four coal fired plants of capacity 600MW each and six gas fired plants with capacity 400 MW each [7].

TABLE II. INPUT DATA FOR ECONOMIC CALCULATION

No.	Parameters	Unit	Power Plant Fuel Types		
			Nuclear	Coal	Gas
1	Net electric power output	kW(e)	2 X 1200	4X600	6X400
2	Construction Time	years	6	4	3
3	Plant lifetime	years	60	30	30
4	Average load factor	-	0.9	0.8	0.8
5	Decommissioning cost	mills/kW	1	-	-
6	Overnight cost	\$/kW(e)	5000	1500	1000
7	Capital investment schedule				
	First Year	%	2	15	30
	Second Year	%	14.6	30	50
	Third Year	%	22	30	20
	Fourth Year	%	24.4	25	-
	Fifth Year	%	21.7	-	-
	Sixth Year	%	15.3	-	-

All three power plant types have approximately the same power output. The main sources of these input data are for fossil fuel power plants and international market values collected from different sources along with data used for previous similar cases.

LUEC, defined as the costs per unit of electricity generated, which is the ratio of total lifetime expenses and the total expected output, expressed in terms of present value equivalent [8]. LUEC (C) is equivalent to the average price that would have to be paid by consumers to repay the investor (utility) exactly the expenditures for capital (CI_t), O&M ($O&M_t$) and fuel (F_t), with a proper discount rate (r) for the time period of t_0 to t . Over the plant lifetime (P_t) with a fixed load-factor (Lf_t) LUEC can be calculated using Eq. 1 and Eq. 2.

$$\sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{CI_t + O&M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}} = \sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} C \frac{P_t \cdot 8760 \cdot Lf_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}} \quad (1)$$

$$C = \frac{\sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{CI_t + O&M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}}}{\sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{P_t \cdot 8760 \cdot Lf_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}}} \quad (2)$$

The levelized net income (NI) is also called net present value (NPV) if the electricity price is constant in terms of 'real money a constant reference price per unit of electricity sold to the customer, which is called PUES [9] and can be obtained from Eq. 3 and Eq. 4.

$$NI(t_0, r, R_t) = \sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{P_t \cdot 8760 \cdot Lf_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}} \cdot R_t - \sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{CI_t + O&M_t + F_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}} \quad (3)$$

$$NI(t_0, r) = (PUES - LUEC) \sum_{t=t_{STSR T}}^{t_{END}} \frac{P_t \cdot 8760 \cdot Lf_t}{(1+r)^{t-t_0}} \quad (4)$$

Calculations have been carried out using the input data in Table II and a tool of the NESA support package called NEST (NESA Economic Support Tool), which has been provided by IAEA [10]. As proposed in the INPRO Manual for Economics in Volume 2 of the report IAEA-TECDOC-1575 Rev.1 and its update, for the three types of plant to be compared in Bangladesh, the following economic parameters were calculated as shown in Table III. Levelized unit electricity costs, internal rate of return, return of investment, total investment volume and investment limit.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF ECONOMIC PARAMETER CALCULATION

Indicators	unit	Abbreviation	Value
Levelized unit electricity cost	cent(Tk)/kW.h	C_N	9.48(7.34)
- NPP AES		C_{A1}	9.13(7.07)
- Coal Power Plant		C_{A2}	8.77(6.79)
- Natural Gas Power Plant			
Internal Rate of Return			
- NPP AES	-	IRR_N	0.016
- Coal Power Plant	-	IRR_{A1}	0.151
- Natural Gas Power Plant	-	IRR_{A2}	0.225
Return of Investment			
- NPP AES	-	ROI_N	0.124
- Coal Power Plant	-	ROI_{A1}	0.113
- Natural Gas Power Plant	-	ROI_{A2}	0.128
Investment volume/limit			
- NPP AES	10 ⁹ \$	INV_N	14708/5184
- Coal Power Plant	10 ⁹ \$	INV_{A1}	2880/3456
- Natural Gas Power Plant	10 ⁹ \$	INV_{A2}	2671/1296

The levelized unit electricity cost LUEC consists of three factors, the capital costs, the operation and maintenance costs (O&M), and the fuel costs. LUEC is equivalent to the price of electricity that would have to be paid by consumers to repay exactly all costs for capital, O&M and for fuel supply with a proper discount rate and without considering profits. A comparison of levelized cost of electricity obtained from different studies during the last ten years along with this study is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Levelized cost of electricity (LUEC) from different studies

CONCLUSION

The LUEC of the planned NPP AES-2006 is comparable with respect to gas and coal based power plants in Bangladesh. Taking strategic considerations into account — such as security of supply by diversification of energy sources — sufficient attractiveness for an investment in the nuclear power project has been confirmed via the high enough internal rate of return evaluation of the risk associated with an investment in nuclear power in Bangladesh produced the following mixed results: There is a strong commitment by the Government to nuclear power, which is an important prerequisite for a successful nuclear power program. Sufficient robustness of economic results especially for levelized unit electricity cost, for the

planned nuclear technology of AES-2006 has been clearly demonstrated. The key outcomes of this analysis are:

- The levelized unit electricity cost from nuclear source is in comparable range with coal or gas.
- The IRR from nuclear is the lowest due to huge investment cost and relatively longer period of time required for return of investment.
- Excellent ROI expected if the plant could be operated in maximum plant factor up to expected life time.

It can be concluded that the planned nuclear power program in Bangladesh is in partial agreement with the economic requirements of the INPRO methodology. In order to get a complete picture, assessment study in all other aspects is mandatory. It is necessary to perform those studies in near future so that Bangladesh can adopt the ideal mechanism to materialize its dream of becoming a successful user of nuclear energy for electricity generation in a sustainable manner.

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